

Several Properties of the Polymer Cement Concrete Using Polypropylene Emulsion

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ABSTRACT

Several polymer emulsions are mixed into concrete to improve its physical and mechanical properties. In this paper, we report the results of several experiment aimed at investigating the effect of polypropylene polymer emulsion on consistency and air entrainment in fresh concrete, and on several physical properties, compressive, tensile, flexural strength, durability against freezing and thawing action and the dependence of flexural strength on temperature in hardened concrete. Adhesive strength of the polymer emulsion to concrete and other materials was also investigated in this study.

INTRODUCTION

It has been pointed out that polymer is one of the important construction materials. Polymer is used with portland cement as a polymer cement concrete in order to improve several physical and mechanical properties of concrete such as tensile and flexural strength, permeability, drying shrinkage, and durability against freezing and thawing, and against various chemical actions. The polymer emulsion used in polymer cement concrete should be easily mixed into a mixture composed of cement and water, resulting in the development of adhesive strength by drying.

The polymer used in this study is a kind of polypropylene emulsion, which is mainly composed of polypropylene and bitumenous substances. Previous studies concerning the polymer cement concrete using this polymer emulsion showed that the polypropylene polymer emulsion is effective in decreasing drying shrinkage and water absorption capacity, and in increasing the resistance against freezing and thawing, and sulphate solution action ^{1),2),3)}.

The first part of this paper reports the results of the investigations carried out to clarify the effects of polymer-cement ratio on the unit cement content for a given slump and on the air content of concrete. In the second part of this paper, the results of flexural strength tests of the polymer cement concrete carried out at - 5°C, 20°C and 50°C are reported to clarify the dependence of mechanical property of the polymer cement concrete on temperature.

Polymer emulsions are used as an adhesive to reinforce concrete structures.

The effectiveness of the polypropylene polymer emulsion as a adhesive for bonding steel and veneer plates to concrete is also discussed in the last part of this paper.

OUTLINE OF EXPERIMENT

Materials and Mix Proportion of Concrete

The polypropylene polymer emulsion used in this study is composed of polypropylene and bitumen. The cement used is a ordinary portland cement. The coarse and fine aggregates used for making concrete are crushed stone (maximum size : 25 mm, specific gravity : 2.62, absorption capacity : 1.5 %) and river sand (specific gravity : 2.60, absorption capacity : 2.3 %, finess modulus : 3.13), respectively. Unit water content of the concretes was determined so as to obtain the slumps of 5 cm and 18 cm for the unit cement contents of 250 kg/m³, 300 kg/m³ and 350 kg/m³. The content of the polymer emulsion is from 2 percent to 10 percent by weight of cement. The polymer emulsion was diluted with water before it was mixed into concrete.

Procedures of Experiment

Compressive and Tensile Strength Test

The cylindrical specimens, 10 cm in diameter and 20 cm in height, were prepared for the compressive and tensile strength tests, which were carried out according to JIS A 1108 and 1113.

Flexual Strength Test

The prismatic specimens, 10 by 10 by 40 cm, were prepared for flexual strength test. The flexual tests at - 5°C, 20°C and 50°C were carried out under a third-point loading in the box in which a constant temperature is maintained, as shown in Fig . 1.

Freezing and Thawing Test

The prismatic specimens, 10 by 10 by 40 cm, for freezing and thawing test were cured in water at 20°C until the age of 14 days. The specimens were subjected to the repeated cycles of freezing and thawing according to ASTM C 666-75.

Adhesion Test

The adhesive strength between concrete, and steel and veneer plates was measured by a flexual strength test method using the prismatic specimens, 10 by 10 by 40 cm, to which the plates were bonded by the polymer emulsion, as shown in Fig. 2. On the other hand, the adhesive strength between asphalt concrete and steel plates was evaluated by the shear strength test for the cylindrical specimens, 10 cm in diameter and 5 cm in height, as shown in Fig. 3.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Relationship between Polymer-Cement Ratio and Unit Water Content, Air Content

As shown in Fig. 4, the air content of the polymer cement concrete increases with polymer-cement ratio. The air entrainment is greater in the concrete made to obtain the slump of 18 cm than the slump of 5 cm.

Fig. 1. Appearance of the equipment used in flexual strength test.

1. Specimen of Concrete
2. Layer of the Polymer Emulsion
3. Steel (or Veneer) Plate
4. Strain Gauge

Fig. 2. Method of adhesive strength test between concrete, and steel and veneer plates by the polymer emulsion.

This result shows that the air entrainment by this polymer emulsion is remarkable in wet concrete.

A SEM micrograph indicates that numerous air bubbles entrained by this polymer emulsion range from 40 μm to 60 μm in size, as shown in Fig. 5. It appears that the air bubbles entrained into concrete influence the consistency of the polymer cement concrete.

The unit water content required for obtaining a given slump lineally decreases with polymer-cement ratio, as shown in Fig. 6. Reduction of unit water content by the addition of the polymer emulsion is the most remarkable in the concrete with the slump of 18 cm and with the unit cement content of 250 kg/m^3 .

Generally speaking, the increase of 1% in air content decreases the unit water content by 3% in usual AE concrete.

Therefore, the polymer emulsion used in this study for reducing the unit water content is more effective than AE admixture in usual concrete.

1. Specimen of Asphalt Concrete
2. Steel Plate Painted by Polymer Emulsion
3. Loading Equipment
4. Load Gauge
5. Oil Jack

Fig. 3. Method of adhesive strength test between asphalt concrete and steel plates.

Fig. 5. SEM micrograph of the polymer cement concrete at the age of 7 days.

Fig. 4. Variations in air content with polymer-cement ratio.

Fig. 6. Variations in unit water content for a given slump with polymer-cement ratio.

Strength and Durability

As shown in Fig. 7, all of the polymer cement concrete with polymer-cement ratio of 2 % shows an increase in compressive strength. The compressive strength of the polymer cement concrete with the slump of 18 cm and with the unit cement content of 250 kg/m³ is greater by 50 % than that of the additive-free concrete. However, the compressive strength of the polymer cement concrete with the slump of 5 cm and with the unit cement content of 300 kg/m³ and 350 kg/m³ decreases as polymer-cement ratio increases.

The ratio of tensile strength to compressive strength in the polymer cement concrete ranges from 1/8 to 1/12. Variations of the tensile strength with polymer-cement ratio are given in Fig. 8.

Fig. 7. Variations in compressive strength at the age of 28 days with polymer-cement ratio.

Fig. 9. SEM micrograph of the polymer cement concrete at the age of 7 days.

Fig. 8. Variations in tensile strength at the age of 28 days with polymer-cement ratio.

Fig. 10. Relationship between compressive strength at the age of 28 days and cement-void ratio.

Taking into considerations the fact that compressive strength in usual concrete decreases by 4 % to 6 % as air content increases by 1 %, the above results show that the strength of concrete is considerably improved by the addition of the polymer emulsion. The improvement results from both the reduction in unit water content and the formation of bond among the constituents by polymer film as shown in Fig. 9. As shown in Fig. 10, there is a linear relationship between compressive strength and cement-void ratio in the polymer cement concrete.

The polymer cement concrete shows a considerably great resistance against freezing and thawing cycles, as shown in Fig. 11.

It appears that the air bubbles entrained by the polymer emulsion is effective in improving the resistance against freezing and thawing action.

Dependence of Flexural Strength on Temperature

As shown in Fig. 12, the flexural strength of the polymer cement concrete at 20°C is maximum at the polymer-cement ratio of 5 % except for the polymer cement concrete with the slump of 5 cm and with the unit cement content of 350 kg/m³. The flexural strength of the polymer cement concrete at - 5°C and 50

Fig. 11. Resistance of the polymer cement concrete against freezing and thawing cycles.

Fig. 12. Variations in flexural strength of the polymer cement concrete at - 5°C, 20°C and 50°C with polymer-cement ratio.

°C considerably reduces at the polymer-cement ratio of 5 % and 10 %.

On the other hand, the polymer cement concrete with the polymer-cement ratio of 2 % shows a remarkable increase in flexural strength at - 5°C. However, the differences in flexural strength between the polymer-cement ratios at 50°C are

Fig. 13. Adhesive strength between concrete and steel plate by the polymer emulsion.

Fig. 14. Adhesive strength between concrete and veneer plate by the polymer emulsion.

Fig. 15. Adhesive strength between asphalt concrete and steel plate by the polymer emulsion and usual tar.

Fig. 16. Adhesive strength between asphalt concrete and steel plate by the mixture of the polymer emulsion and portland cement.

not so great as those at - 5°C. The results indicate that the flexural strength of the polymer cement concrete considerably depends on temperature.

Adhesive Strength between Concrete and Other Materials with the Polymer Emulsion

As shown in Fig. 13, the polymer emulsion is not effective as an adhesive between concrete and steel plates. However, as shown in Fig. 14, the polymer emulsion is effective for adhesion between concrete and veneer plates.

The polymer emulsion used in this study contains a large quantity of water. Therefore, the effect of the polymer emulsion on its adhesive strength to other materials appears not to come out until water in the polymer emulsion evaporates in some degree. The polymer emulsion is more effective as an adhesive with a hygroscopic material such as a veneer plate.

Furthermore, as shown in Fig. 15, the adhesive strength between asphalt concrete and steel plates with the polymer emulsion increases as the amount of the polymer emulsion painted increases. However, the adhesive strength of the polymer emulsion is smaller than that of usual tar.

On the other hand, the adhesive strength between asphalt concrete and steel plates is increased by adding portland cement to the polymer emulsion, as shown in Fig. 16. The effectiveness of the addition of cement seems to result from the increase in adhesive strength due to consumption of water in the polymer emulsion by the hydration of cement and from the cementation by the hydrated portland cement.

CONCLUSIONS

The main results obtained are as follows.

- 1) The polymer emulsion entrains air in concrete. The air entrainment of the polymer emulsion is greater than that of usual AE admixture.
- 2) The effects of the polymer emulsion on strength and durability are remarkable in the polymer cement concrete with small cement content.
- 3) The strength of the polymer cement concrete strongly correlates with cement-void ratio .
- 4) The polymer cement concrete shows a great increase in the flexural strength at a low temperature at an appropriate polymer-cement ratio. However, the flexural strength of the polymer cement concrete is relatively low at a high temperature.
- 5) The effectiveness of the polymer emulsion as an adhesive is remarkable in the adhesion between hygroscopic materials.

In this paper, we deal with the polymer cement concrete with portland cement. This polymer emulsion is found to be also effective in blastfurnace slag cement concrete by several experiments carried out in another study.

REFERENCES

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